

POLICY BRIEF

Overview of Policy, Legal and Institutional Environment for Food Safety Management in the Informal Sector in Africa

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Co-funded by
the European Union

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Key messages

- The African informal food sector plays an important role in food provisioning; however, it is inadequately regulated posing significant food safety and public health risks.
- Several policy frameworks and initiatives exist at the continental, regional and national levels to enhance food control systems.
- Implementation of existing legal frameworks in the informal sector is hindered by fragmented institutional oversight, limited technical and infrastructural capacity and absence of tailored policies that consider the realities of informal actors.
- Given the characteristics of the informal food sector, distinct enforcement strategies are necessary compared to those used in the formal sector.
- The FS4Africa project will identify and promote innovative and best practices for food safety management in the informal food sector

1. Introduction

Food safety is a major public health issue due to the rise of foodborne hazards from domestic and international trade. The World Health Organisation (2015) estimates that 31 food safety hazards together result in over 600 million illnesses and 420,000 deaths each year. Ensuring food safety requires appropriate enabling environments, namely policies, legislations, institutions and other support systems such as capacity enhancement and monitoring. In several African countries, the regulatory framework does not strongly address the informal sector. Consequently, food safety compliance among informal actors is low leading to high prevalence of food contamination, which affects health, food security, and trade.

In Africa, the informal food sector (IFS) plays a pivotal role in food provision, employing 86% of the workforce in Sub-Saharan Africa and 67.3% in North Africa (ILO, 2018). However, this sector presents distinct challenges, requiring risk-based approaches to ensure food safety. The IFS serves as a critical source of income and employment and encompasses all food-related activities outside formal regulatory frameworks and contributes significantly to the economy, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where it accounts for an average of 35% of GDP (ILO, 2018; Jaffee & Henson, 2024). Key activities include street vending, small-scale production, and local markets, which also hold cultural significance.

Despite its importance, the inadequate regulation of the sector and unsafe working conditions pose significant food safety and public health risks. Many informal businesses face barriers such as limited access to resources, education, and training, making compliance with food safety requirements a persistent challenge.

2. The Food Safety for Africa (FS4Africa) Project

The Food Safety for Africa (FS4Africa) [<https://foodsafety4africa.eu/>] project aims to improve African food safety systems with particular attention to the informal sector. This initiative aims to transform local markets, improve food security, and promote regional trade while mitigating adverse effects on the environment, biodiversity, health, and society. The project applies newly developed innovative approaches, convergence strategies and stable partnerships to promote food safety. Among several objectives, the project seeks to review and assess gaps in the current food safety related policies, legal and institutional frameworks at continental, regional and national levels and to examine and identify best practices in creating an enabling environment for food safety management especially in the informal sector.

This policy brief provides key issues identified through key informant interviews and desk reviews of policies, legislation, and institutional frameworks. It highlights the nature of the enabling environment supporting food safety in the informal sector focusing on the continental, regional and some national frameworks. It also identifies key gaps and proposes the way forward to enhance regulatory oversight for food safety in the informal food sector.

3. Key policy frameworks and initiatives at the continental level

There is a high-level continental support for food safety as evident in the AU Member States' adoption of the Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) Framework for Africa (2019-2024) which among others seeks to support Member States' efforts to establish harmonized science-based SPS systems in line with international standards and regional conditions. The framework serves as a guide to operationalizing the SPS Measures in the Annex 7 of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) Agreement.

Furthermore, the SPS framework provided impetus for the development of the Food Safety, Plant Health and Animal Health Strategies for Africa. One of the strategic objectives of the Food Safety Strategy for Africa (2022-2036) is to improve food safety and quality policies, legal and institutional frameworks. This includes enhancing the capacity for the formulation and implementation of food safety policy at national and regional levels and supporting member states in operationalising regulatory innovations in the informal food sector.

The high-level commitment to promoting food safety was further demonstrated with AU Member States' adoption of the Statute for the Establishment of the Africa Food Safety Agency (AfFSA). The functions of the Agency shall include advocacy, guidance and support for the modernization of national food safety systems through policy, legislative and institutional frameworks, and advocating for investment and collaboration with relevant institutions to enhance the competitiveness of African food commodities and products. The Agency will also complement the work being done by Codex Coordinating Committee for Africa (CCAFRICA) and African Organization for Standardization (ARSO) in coordinating food safety issues regarding the promotion of international and regional standards. The Partnership for Aflatoxin Control in Africa (PACA) at the Africa Union Commission has supported 11 Member States including Egypt, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, and Zambia to develop costed evidence-based food safety master plans to strengthen national food safety systems.

These SPS and food safety policy frameworks and other initiatives have been aligned with various continental and international frameworks such as the Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Program (CAADP) framework, WTO SPS and Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Agreements, the requirements of the Codex Alimentarius Commission, the WHO Global Food Safety Strategy and the Sustainable Development Goals.

4. Key Policy Frameworks at the Regional levels

At the regional levels, several strategies and frameworks exist to improve food safety governance. They include the Food Safety Strategy for the Southern African Development Community (SADC), SPS Regulation of the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) and Harmonized Regional Regulations (C/REG.21/11/10) of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) that focuses on the structural and operational rules for plant health, animal health and food safety. Others are the SPS protocol in East African Community (EAC) and the Regional SPS Strategy in the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD), which aims to harmonize SPS measures across the region, facilitating trade and promoting food safety and agricultural development. The EAC also has regional food standards that are adaptable by member states, however, each country voluntarily implements the proposed standards.

The Regional Economic Communities (RECs) have initiated various programmes to support member states to improve food control and governance. Examples are the proposal to establish the ECOWAS Technical Harmonization Committee to among others support the development, harmonization and maintenance of standards and the COMESA's 11th European Development Fund (EDF) Trade Facilitation Programme, which among others seeks to build political support and sustainable mechanisms for a process of harmonization of food safety requirements based on risk assessment in selected pilot countries.

5. Key policies, legal and institutional frameworks at national levels

This section covers Egypt, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria and South Africa where the FS4Africa project is being implemented. These countries have ratified numerous legislation and policy documents addressing food safety to promote public health and domestic, regional and international trade. Some of the policies and legislation are presented in Annex 1. Collectively, these national regulations aim to create a robust foundation for ensuring a safe and sanitary food environment. However, despite this comprehensive legislative framework, several limitations persist in the regulatory system. Many aspects of the framework require alignment with international standards and principles. Key gaps include the insufficient integration of risk management systems covering the entire food supply chain, including the adoption of good agricultural, hygiene, and manufacturing practices. Addressing these gaps is critical to enhancing the effectiveness of food safety legislation. Additionally, policies and legal frameworks frequently focus on the formal sector, resulting in inconsistent enforcement and practices in informal markets.

Egypt's Ministry of Health and Population and its agencies play a crucial role in the national food control system. Food safety laws and regulations are enforced by several ministries: Ministry of Health and Population (MOPH), Ministry of Agriculture (MALR), Ministry of Trade and Industry (MTI), and Ministry of Supply and Internal Trade. The Ministry of Health and Population (MOHP) is responsible for the implementation of Basic Laws 281/94 and 10/1966. In addition, several ministerial decrees have been issued by the Ministry of Health and Population, particularly around food additives.

Currently, the issue of food safety has attracted a great deal of interest from the public and has become one of the top priorities for decision-makers in the Egyptian government. The adoption of the Food Safety Law, which followed the adoption of Law N1/2017 establishing the National Food Safety Authority (NFSA) by the Egyptian Parliament, was an important step. It is important that once this authority is in place, the food safety system, the capacity of analytical laboratories and risk analysis based on food inspection are modernised, strengthened and maintained.

The NFSA's responsibility for food is defined based on the definition of food outlined in Law 1, which aligns with the Codex Alimentarius definition. While the NFSA is primarily responsible for the enforcement of national food legislation, they can delegate authority to the Department of Food Safety and Control under the Ministry of Health and Population to ensure adequate coverage. This collaborative administration ensures effective supervision, control, and timely follow-up actions. Despite the good progress, challenges remain in the implementation of these regulations, including:

- (i) **Responsibility overlaps:** Egypt successfully resolved overlaps in responsibilities by designating the Ministry of Agriculture for pre-harvest food safety and the NFSA for post-harvest food safety.
- (ii) **Conflicts in Authority:** Law No. 92 of 2018 complicates the system by assigning responsibilities to non-specialized entities such as the New Urban Communities Authority (under the Ministry of Housing) and local governments.
- (iii) **Limited Technical expertise:** These entities lack the technical expertise required for effective food safety regulation, hindering the achievement of desired outcomes.

Ghana has several pieces of legislation governing food safety, including Public Health Act 2012 (Act 815) of the Ministry of Health, which mandates the Food and Drugs Authority (FDA) to provide and enforce standards for food safety. The FDA is required to monitor and ensure compliance with provisions on food safety in collaboration with the Municipal Assemblies and other agencies. The Act permits the

FDA to develop guidelines and regulations including various guidelines on inspections and monitoring for industry compliance. Other regulatory and competent authorities are the Ghana Standards Authority (GSA), Environmental Protection Authority (EPA), Fisheries Commission (FC), Veterinary Services Directorate (VSD), and Plant Protection and Regulatory Services Directorate (PPRSD). These are governed by various legislations and legislative instruments such as Meat Inspection Regulation 2020 (LI 2405), Fisheries Regulations 2010 (L.I. 1968), Registration and Licensing of Food, Beverage and Entertainment Enterprise Regulations 2016 (LI 2238) and Plants and Fertilizer (Aflatoxin Control in Maize Grain) Technical Regulations 2020 (LI 2428).

However, analysis of the frameworks shows that the roles of institutions along the food value chain, including production, harvesting, post-harvest storage, processing, distribution, marketing, and food services, are not clearly defined. Thus, the National Food Safety Policy adopted in 2021 sets out the roles of various institutions including the Judiciary, Parliament, Ministries, Agencies and Departments and the private sector in food safety management. To strengthen coordination among sectors, an Intersectoral Food Safety Coordinating Committee (NIFSCC) was established. Furthermore, the Food Safety Technical Working Group was formed to oversee the implementation of the strategic plan of the policy and to develop harmonized guidelines and other operational documents.

Already, the Food Safety Technical Working Group, comprising all the regulators and competent authorities, has developed harmonized import and export procedures for implementation and is assessing competent authorities' institutional mandates to streamline them, eliminate duplication of efforts and ensure clear distinctions in mandates.

In addition to these regulators and competent authorities, various stakeholders are involved in ensuring food safety. A comprehensive stakeholders' net mapping undertaken in Ghana has identified eleven categories of actors:

1. Global, Continental and Regional Policy, Regulatory and Standards Stakeholders
2. Ministries, Departments and Agencies
3. National Regulators and Competent Authorities
4. Donors and Development Partners
5. International Research Organisations
6. Advocacy Players
7. Research, Academia, and Professional Associations
8. Informal value chain actors
9. Formal value chain actors
10. Media
11. Consumers

The analysis showed that all the food regulators and competent authorities are mandated to regulate both the formal and informal sectors. However, over the years, less attention has focused on the informal sector due to various challenges including limited logistics and a lack of a proper register of informal food actors.

Kenya's legal framework is relatively fragmented, governed by various acts such as the Public Health Act (Cap 242, Revised Ed. 2012) and the Food, Drugs and Chemical Substances Act (Cap 254 of 1965). Inspection and enforcement responsibilities are distributed among agencies like the Kenya Plant Health Inspectorate Service (KEPHIS) and the Directorate of Veterinary Services (DVS). The Kenya Bureau of Standards (KEBS) serves as the sole standard-setting authority while the Ministry of Health plays a central role in enforcement. Municipalities in Kenya struggle to provide the necessary infrastructure for

safe food handling in informal markets. About 60% of informal vendors in Nairobi lack access to basic sanitation facilities and clean water (Mazi et al., 2023).

Nigeria has spread its food safety mandate across 13 Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs). The National Food Safety Policy also articulates the roles of State ministries and Local Government Areas (LGAs), which are the lowest levels of government. States and Local government agencies are expected to reach most of the country's population, especially those living in the rural areas. The effective implementation of the legal and institutional framework depends on the competence of the responsible structures at each level.

At the federal level, more than a dozen ministries, departments and agencies oversee food safety policy. Principally, the national food safety regulation and standardization are led by the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) and the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). Laws conferring powers on managing authorities often use imprecise terms, leading to overlapping responsibilities. In addition to confusion about roles and responsibilities, the acts and policies are old, which justifies the importance of revising them in line with innovations and best practices. Regulatory efforts should focus on revising outdated policies and clarifying roles and responsibilities among more than a dozen ministries, departments and agencies at the federal level.

South Africa's regulatory and legislative framework and food control system have several strengths which contribute to the effective management of food safety. They aim to establish the general principles, organizational arrangements and procedures for ensuring plant, animal and food safety. However, certain aspects are the responsibility of different national government departments such as National Department of Health (DOH), Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF), Department of Trade, Industry and Competition (DTIC), National Regulator for Compulsory Specifications (NRCS) and South African Bureau of standards (SABS). Several non-governmental stakeholders and key players are also involved as well as international Organisation including Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), World Health Organization (WHO), World Organization of Animal Health (WOAH), Codex Alimentarius Commission and International Organization for Standardization (ISO). At the local level, there are provincial and municipal legislations enforced to implement national guidelines. Additionally, there are private standards utilized by supermarkets, butchers, dairies, and other retailers of animal products.

6. Challenges of the Informal Sector

While legal frameworks exist, their implementation in the informal sector is hindered by weak governance, lack of resources, and limited technical capacity among food vendors. Institutional oversight is fragmented, with multiple agencies operating without clear coordination. The absence of tailored policies that consider the realities of informal actors further exacerbates food safety risks, including contamination, unhygienic practices, and exposure to foodborne diseases. Other challenges are lack of infrastructure, limited inspection, a high level of informality, inadequate training and education, economic constraints, cultural and social factors, and inefficiency. With regards to infrastructure, the sector often lacks formal structure, record-keeping practices, basic infrastructure and amenities like potable water, waste disposal systems, and unreliable power supply, which make monitoring and enforcement difficult.

In addition, inspection in the informal sector rarely occurs. On the rare occasions that inspections do take place, they tend to be reactive rather than proactive, often triggered by food safety complaints or incidents rather than as part of a regular follow-up process. There is also a high level of informality driven by the lack of proper frameworks for registration and compliance, consequently promoting informal operations

by producers and sellers, making it difficult for regulators to meet and enforce standards.

Without proper training, it is difficult to ensure compliance with food safety standards. However, informal market stakeholders largely constitute individuals who lack the training and education in food safety to facilitate interest and compliance with standards. The situation has increased interest in stakeholder education and training to potentially encourage widespread involvement by the informal sector in food safety management. Moreover, complying with food safety regulations can be costly making it challenging for small scale actors such as sellers and producers in the informal sector to meet the cost requirements of becoming or being compliant, ultimately driving a strong disinterest in complying with these standards.

There are diverse cultural and social barriers to food safety compliance. For instance, traditional practices and local customs can sometimes conflict with modern food safety regulations. Thus, enhancing acquaintance and adoption of modern practices would require a behavioural nudge and significant awareness-raising, which is difficult to easily implement among the vast representation of the informal sector in the modern African business ecosystem. There are systemic shortfalls like inefficiency within regulatory agencies which often undermine efforts to effectively enforce food safety standards.

7. Regulatory frameworks and initiatives targeting the informal sector

Though food safety policies also target the informal food sector, challenges remain in their implementation, enforcement, and harmonization to encourage local and international trade. However, countries are implementing various scalable initiatives as highlighted in this section.

Egyptian Law No. 92 of 2018, aims to regulate and encourage the operation of mobile catering units. Administrative authority has been delegated to local administrative units, the competent authorities of the New Urban Communities Authority, and other designated administrative entities. This law covers mobile catering units, which include vehicles, carts or mobile platforms equipped for the preparation, cooking or sale of food and meals. In addition, Decision No. 2 of 2019 issued by the NFSA establishes the technical inspection requirements for mobile food units. These requirements include food safety standards, sanitary conditions for workers and licensing procedures required by the Authority. Egypt also has policies that offer microfinancing and loans to businesses in the informal food sector.

Ghana's innovative initiatives include revised legislations that empower Local Governments, Ghana Tourism Authority (GTA), and Food and Drug Authority (FDA) to register, license and regulate informal food sector. Ghana's FDA is implementing the Progressive Licensing Scheme (PLS) for cottage, micro and small-Scale enterprises, most of which are informal. The PLS operates on a risk-based Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) standard, where applicants undergo inspections and receive certification based on their compliance level. Licenses are awarded in three progressive categories: Pink (Level 1) – Initial stage of compliance; Yellow (Level 2) – Intermediate compliance stage; and Green (Level 3) – Full compliance with regulatory standards. This progressive certification system ensures that small and cottage businesses have a clear pathway to achieving full regulatory compliance, promoting safe and high-quality local production. FDA is also implementing the Street Food Vending Permit Initiative where the Code for Hygienic Practice and Guidelines for Licensing formal Foodservice Establishments have been adapted for informal street food vendors. Another initiative is the Food Product Monitoring Programme which entails an expansion of FDA's scope of regulation to include artisanal food industry where high-risk products are regularly monitored in the markets followed by education and training of the actors to ensure compliance with basic food safety requirements.

Kenya's Standards and Market Access Program (SMAP), launched in 2018, aims to assist the country

to minimize risks and hazards related to agricultural products, enhance the quality of local produce and increase the country's export basket and its access to new export markets. The program is expected to enhance market access and competitiveness of Kenya's animal and plant-based products through adoption of relevant international standards and improved food safety regulation and enforcement. The SMAP is jointly implemented by the Kenya Bureau of Standards (KEBS), the Kenya Plant Health Inspectorate Services (KEPHIS), the Department of Veterinary Services (DVS) and the UNIDO.

Nigeria's Regulatory bodies such as National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) and Standards Organisation of Nigeria (SON) play significant roles in regulating and controlling food production, processing, distribution and sale in Nigeria, including the informal markets. They set and enforce food safety standards, NAFDAC conducts inspections and acts against violations. The Federal Ministry of Health (FMOH) works with NAFDAC, as well as State and Local Government agencies. Local Government Councils have a role in enforcing food safety regulations within their jurisdictions. They often work in collaboration with NAFDAC to provide infrastructure for food safety compliance, conduct inspections, and take penalizes violations in informal markets and street food vendors. They face challenges in enforcing food safety standards in this sector due to limited resources, inadequate infrastructure and the sheer scale of informal activities. Many informal food vendors may not be aware of existing food safety regulations or may not prioritize them. As a result, the informal sector often operates with minimal oversight, leading to gaps in food safety governance.

South Africa has developed guidelines and frameworks for the regulation of informal trade within the municipalities. These regulations are designed to ensure that informal traders operate in accordance with their permits. The responsibilities of the South African Local Government Association (SALGA) include providing critical infrastructure to support informal traders, such as access to clean water and waste disposal facilities.

8. Addressing Regulatory Gaps Through a Human Rights Lens

While formal food safety frameworks exist across the continent, millions of people continue to operate and consume within informal food systems that lack adequate regulatory oversight. This gap in protection disproportionately affects marginalised groups, including low-income households, women and children – many of whom rely on the informal sector for both livelihoods and nutrition.

From a human rights perspective, this raises significant concerns. The right to food, the right to health, and broader socio-economic rights enshrined in the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, the Maputo Protocol, and various international treaties are all relevant. When regulatory frameworks fail to extend protection to the informal sector, they risk perpetuating inequality and violating states' obligations to uphold these rights.

Framing food safety as a human rights issue also shifts the conversation from technical reform to transformative justice. It requires that policies be not only effective but also equitable, inclusive, and participatory – placing people, not just products, at the centre of reform.

9. Conclusion & Recommendations

In most cases, the existing policies and legislations do not distinguish between formal and informal food sector – both sectors must comply with the same laid down requirements to ensure food safety and protect public health. Given the characteristics of the informal food sector, which encompass “all food-related activities that are unregistered, unregulated, and frequently operate outside the parameters of formal market structures, including all actors and stages of the food chain,” distinct enforcement strategies are necessary compared to those used in the formal sector. Hence, countries must develop strategies to enhance food control in the informal sector. These innovative approaches may include:

- Customised regulations
- Co-regulation where food vendors and regulators work together to encourage voluntary compliance
- Tailored capacity-building programmes
- Community-based strategies
- Public-private partnerships
- Application of low-cost technologies in food safety management
- Consumer education to create a demand for safer food.

The FS4Africa project aims to explore the best practices and innovative approaches that enhance food safety management in the informal sector, hence further interrogation and consultations will be done to identify several best practices. This will be followed by engagement with national, subregional and continental policy stakeholders to co-develop recommendations that are adaptive and context-specific and balance food safety priorities with the socio-economic realities of the informal sector.

References

- International Labour Organization (ILO). (2018). *Women and men in the informal economy: A statistical picture*. Third edition.
- Jaffee, S., & Henson, S. (2024). Promoting Food Safety in the Informal Markets of Low-and Middle-Income Countries: The Need for a Rethink. *Food Protection Trends*, 44(5).
- Mazi, I. M., Onyeaka, H., Akegbe, H., Njoagwuani, E. I., Ochulor, C. E., Oladunjoye, I. O., & Odeyemi, O. A. (2023). Street vended foods in Nigeria: An analysis of the current state of affairs and the way forward. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2023.2266194>
- WHO (2015). *WHO estimates of the global burden of foodborne diseases: Foodborne disease burden epidemiology reference group 2007-2015*. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization.

Annex 1 Some Legal Frameworks in Egypt, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria and South Africa

LEGAL FRAMEWORK	DESCRIPTION
Egypt	
Constitution of the Arab Republic of Egypt – Article 79	Guarantees citizens’ right to safe food and water; commits state to food sovereignty and agricultural biodiversity.
Law No. 1 of 2017	Establishes National Food Safety Authority (NFSA) as primary food control body. NFSA has issued several mandatory technical regulations to establish Maximum Residue Levels (MRLs) for key food contaminants.
Ministerial Decree No. 1018 of 2013 on the Registration, Handling and Use of Pesticides	This decree defines the roles and powers of the Pesticides Committee, which are to review applications for pesticide registration and certify those that are suitable.
Regulatory Establishments No. 2 of 2019	Establishes the technical requirements for mobile food units such as Decrees on Rules for applying food safety requirements in food establishments; Control system for tourist establishments; Licensing food handling in tourist and hotel establishments; and Requirements for food traceability
Export Food Strategy Mechanism Standards (3 Decrees):	Decree No. 3 of 2019: Inspection and review procedures for certification companies for exported food consignments. Decree No. 1 of 2020: Mandatory rules for issuing export suitability certificates. Decree No. 15 of 2020: Exemption for white-listed factories from labeling certain data on exported food shipments.
Decree No. 2613/1994 on the shelf life of products	This decree establishes a maximum shelf life for products, defined as the period during which the product retains its basic characteristics and remains edible and marketable under the defined packaging, transport and storage conditions.
Ghana	
Constitution of Ghana 1992	By virtue of the Guiding Principles of State Policy, the State is required by Article 36 (10) to safeguard the health, safety and welfare of all persons
Public Health Act 2012 (Act 815)	The FDA formerly, the Food and Drugs Board was established in 1987 by the Food and Drugs Law 1992 (PNDCL 305B). This law has been integrated in Part 7 of the Public Health Act 2012 for the provision and enforcement of food safety standards and other requirements. Part 5 of the Public Health Act mandates the Public and Environmental Health Department of the MMDAs to ensure compliance with food safety and hygiene requirements at the informal sector
Standards decree of 1973 (NRCD 173) Ghana Standards Authority (GSA) Act 2022 (Act 1078)	This decree established Ghana Standards Authority (GSA). This Act gives the GSA more power to enforce standards and prosecute companies that do not adhere to them
Plants and Fertilizer Act, 2010 (Act 803)	This Act established the Plant Protection and Regulatory Services Directorate (PPRSD) responsible for crop pest and disease management, plant quarantine, Pesticide and fertilizer regulation, seed inspection and
Animals (Control of Importation) Act, 1952 No. 36 and the Disease of Animals Act, 1961 (Act 83)	These Acts mandate the Veterinary Services Directorate of MOFA to be responsible for the prevention and control of the spread of infectious and contagious diseases among animals, conduct autopsy on dead animals
Meat Inspection Regulation 2020 (LI 2405)	This LI is a set of regulations that aim to ensure meat and meat products are processed and slaughtered under sanitary conditions. It is implemented by the VSD.
Fisheries Act, 2002 (Act 625)	This Act established the Fisheries Commission under the Ministry of Fisheries and Aquaculture Development (MoFAD).

Fisheries Regulations, 2010 (L.1. 1968)	These are a set of regulations that prescribe measures for the conservation, management, development, licensing and regulation of fisheries. It is implemented by the Fisheries Commission.
Environmental Protection Agency Act, 1994 (ACT490)	This Act established the Environmental Protection Agency to among others control and monitor the use and management of pesticides and hazardous chemicals in food production and related activities.
Local Governance Act, 2016 (Act 936)	This Act governs the operations of the MMDAs. Among others, the Act prohibits the sale or serving of unwholesome food, sale of food under insanitary conditions, and food unfit for consumption.
Tourism Act, 2011 (Act 817)	This Act established the Ghana Tourism Authority as the main institution responsible for the promotion of sustainable development of the tourism sector. GTA regulates food and beverage enterprises through the Registration and Licensing of Food, Beverage and Entertainment Enterprise Regulations, 2016 (LI 2238)
Kenya	
Public Health Act (Cap 242, Revised Ed. 2012)	It provides for the construction and regulation of buildings used for storage of foodstuffs, prohibits residing or sleeping in kitchens or food stores as well as the regulation on public water supplies, meat, milk and other articles of food.
Food Drugs and Chemical Substances Act (Cap 254 of 1965, Amended 2002)	It provides rules for the placing on the market of food and drugs for man and animal, establishes the Public Health (Standards) Board; and makes provision for the control of the quality and safety of food, drugs and chemical substances to be placed on the market of Kenya. It prohibits the labelling, packaging, sale, treatment and processing of food that does not meet a prescribed standard.
Nigeria	
National Health Act	Provides a framework for the regulation, development and administration of a national health system and sets standards for the provision of health services in the Federation and other related matters.
Animal Disease Control Act	An animal disease control and prevention act aimed at preventing the introduction and spread of infectious and contagious diseases among animals, hatcheries and poultry in Nigeria.
The Milk Substitutes Marketing Act	This Act seeks to promote optimum protection of infants and young children in matters relating to food safety.
Pesticide Registration Regulations 2021	The Regulations provide requirements for the labeling (including instructions for use) of pesticides.
The Food, Drugs and Related Products (Registration, etc.) Act	The Act regulates the manufacture, import, export, advertising, sale or distribution of processed food, drugs and related products and their registration.
South Africa	
Law n° 54 of 1972 on food products, cosmetics and disinfectants	This act regulates the production, marketing and import of all foodstuffs from the point of view of public health and safety.
Law n° 63 of 1977 on Health	It regulates aspects relating to the hygiene of buildings in contact with foodstuffs (including milking sheds) and their transport.
Law n° 28 of 1974 on international health regulations	It also specifies the hygienic conditions that must be met when handling food.
Law n° 28 of 1974 on international health regulations	It aims to control and promote the safety of agricultural products and to develop quality assurance standards (particularly for meat, dairy products, cereals, certain canned goods, fruit and vegetables) for domestic and export markets.
Law n° 101 of 1965 on drugs and related substances	This law regulates, among other things, the approval of veterinary drugs, as well as foods and dietary supplements that affect health or make health claims.

Law n° 36 of 1947 fertilizers, animal feeds and products used to improve agriculture and livestock farming	This act governs everything to do with animals and animal products, including meat, milk, eggs and products made from them, from an animal health perspective.
Law n° 35 of 1984 on animal diseases	This act governs all aspects relating to animals and animal products, including meat, milk, eggs and products derived from them, from an animal health perspective.
Law n° 36 of 1983 on crop pests	Under this law, any South African citizen may import plants and plant products, provided that such imports do not pose a risk to the agro-industry, forestry or the environment

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Funding for this policy brief has been provided by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme FS4Africa (Grant Agreement Number: 101136916) and New Frontiers in Research Fund (NFRF).

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Funded by the European Union and New Frontiers in Research Fund (NFRF). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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ISSN 3057-3785

9 773 057 378 002 1